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Environmental Management Accounting and Operating Performance of Listed Oil Companies: A Longitudinal Study in an Emerging Economy

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Abstract: *This research examines the correlation between the implementation of EMA and the operating performance of Nigerian oil companies on the stock exchange for the year 2014-2023. The study assesses the level of implementation of the EMA practices in these companies and analyses the changes in its financial and non-financial performance measures. This study employed longitudinal and ex-post facto research designs, secondary data were collected from the annual reports and financial statements of the listed oil companies in Nigeria. Data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, which include panel data regression analysis to measure the significance and direction of the relationship among these variables. We employed both fixed and random effects models to determine the relationship between EMA, LEV, SIZE, and performance indicators. The results show that, although awareness exists on the role of environmental management accounting for the Nigerian oil industry, there is still limited application and implementation in corporate strategies. Further, the results show that EMA does not exert immediate significant impact of financial performance of Nigerian firms, especially in sectors like oil where traditional operations are deeply embedded. The concluded that while EMA practices are essential for long-term sustainability, their immediate financial benefits may be limited, especially in the context of the Nigerian oil industry. As the Nigerian oil sector continues to evolve, future studies could explore the longer-term effects of EMA adoption and the changing role of market forces in driving sustainability efforts.*

Keywords: *Financial Performance; Non-Financial Performance; Sustainability; Environmental; Accounting.*

1. Introduction

To what extent does the adoption of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) practices impact the operating performance of listed oil companies in Nigeria? This question is critical and has gained significant attention in recent years as environmental sustainability becomes a focal point in corporate governance, especially within environmentally sensitive industries such as oil and gas as the oil sector which plays a significant role in Nigeria's economy, contributing significantly to the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) and government revenues (Ebimobowei, 2022). The oil and gas sector are also at the centre of environmental concerns due to the extractive nature of the industry. This increasing global focus on environmental accountability has spurred interest in how industries with high environmental impact, such as oil and gas, adopt sustainable practices like EMA (James & Sylvester, 2023). Thus, the need for oil companies to integrate environmental considerations into their accounting practices has become increasingly urgent. EMA provides a framework for businesses to identify,

manage, and report environmental costs and impacts, which can influence both financial and non-financial performance.

EMA has emerged as a critical tool for businesses seeking to align their operations with sustainable practices (Medeckytė & Daiva, 2023). EMA involves the identification, collection, and analysis of environmental costs and performance data, integrating them into conventional accounting systems. This approach not only enhances a company's environmental stewardship but also provides a clear picture of the financial implications of its environmental activities (Esther & Isaiah, 2023). In essence, EMA enables firms to manage their environmental costs more effectively which often leads to improved operational and financial performance (Gerged et al., 2024). In Nigeria, the enhancement of EMA practices in oil companies is a growing trend (Polycarp, 2019). As the Nigerian government increases the stringency of its environmental legislation and the global community becomes more particular about the environmental accountability of companies, Nigeria's oil companies are bearing the burden of embracing EMA as a business imperative (Esther & Isaiah, 2023).

Operating performance refers to the efficiency and effectiveness with which a company utilizes its resources to achieve its business objectives (Otu, et al., 2018). It covers all aspects of an organization's activities ranging from organizational performance in terms of productivity, profitability, and market share amongst others, and the extent of organized compliance with regulatory standards (Slack, 2019). Operating performance is typically measured through financial metrics such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS), as well as non-financial metrics such as market size and customer satisfaction. In Nigeria, the operating performance of oil companies has been a subject of considerable interest due to the sector's critical role in the economy (Asagunla & Agbede, 2018). The industry faces numerous challenges which includes fluctuating oil prices, regulatory pressures, and environmental concerns. These challenges have prompted oil firms to seek ways to optimize their operations, reduce costs, and improve efficiency (Adeleye et al., 2019). One of the key strategies employed by these firms is the integration of EMA practices into their business processes.

Previous studies have explored the concept of EMA as an essential tool for integrating environmental costs into traditional accounting systems, providing insights for companies into both their environmental impacts and associated costs (Schaltegger & Burritt, 2017; Medeckytė & Daiva, 2023). Several empirical studies have demonstrated that firms adopting EMA practices report improved operational performance, reduced environmental impact, and better compliance with regulatory standards (Esther & Isaiah, 2023; Gerged et al., 2024). Furthermore, Schaltegger et al. (2017) highlighted that EMA adoption allows organizations to better account for environmental costs, leading to more informed decision-making and enhanced financial and non-financial outcomes. Similarly, Deegan (2002) emphasized the importance of EMA in fostering corporate transparency and aligning business practices with sustainability goals. In Nigeria, although the government has made strides toward environmental regulation in the oil sector, the adoption of EMA remains limited, contributing to ongoing environmental challenges (Polycarp, 2019). The question remains whether the slow adoption of EMA practices in Nigeria's oil sector significantly hampers the operational efficiency and financial performance of oil companies.

Moreover, despite the increasing focus on EMA, few studies have explicitly examined its effect on the operating performance of oil companies in emerging economies, particularly in the context of Nigeria. The unique regulatory, economic, and environmental challenges faced by oil companies in this region warrant a more detailed investigation. In addition, while several studies have focused on the financial implications of EMA, there remains a gap in understanding how it impacts both financial and non-financial performance in emerging economies. For instance, Burritt et al. (2002) provided valuable insights into how EMA influences corporate environmental strategies, but their work was largely focused on developed countries. In contrast, the current study aims to address this gap by providing empirical evidence from Nigeria, a developing economy with a high reliance on the oil sector. This research is timely, as calls for more context-specific studies on the application and impact of EMA in emerging economies have been growing in recent literature (Christ and Burritt, 2023; Burritt et al., 2019).

Given the limited research on the adoption of EMA in Nigeria's oil industry, this study assesses the extent of EMA adoption and its influence on the operating performance of listed oil companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. While previous research has focused primarily on general environmental accounting practices, there is limited empirical evidence specific to the Nigerian oil sector that connects EMA adoption with financial and non-financial performance metrics such as Return on Assets (ROA), Earnings Per Share (EPS), and market share (Otu et al., 2018). This study thus specifically investigates both the financial and non-financial impacts of EMA adoption. This dual focus provides a more comprehensive understanding of the value of EMA in enhancing overall organizational performance in an industry facing both environmental and economic pressures.

The motivation for this study stems from the critical need to align business practices in Nigeria's oil sector with global environmental sustainability goals. As highlighted by Ebeku (2018), the regulatory frameworks governing environmental management in Nigeria have been insufficiently enforced, leading to inefficiencies in the sector. Moreover, recent studies call for further research to assess the economic and environmental implications of EMA in high-impact industries, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria (Nwokeji, 2019). Shell Nigeria's adoption of EMA practices and the subsequent 15% reduction in operational costs serve as an example of the potential benefits but underscore the need for broader implementation and investigation (Shell Nigeria, 2022).

Methodologically, this study employs a longitudinal study design, utilizing financial and operational data from listed oil companies in Nigeria between 2014 and 2023 to examine the adoption of EMA and its impact on operating performance. This approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of the factors driving EMA adoption and its effects on both financial and non-financial performance. By analysing the extent of EMA adoption and its effects on financial and non-financial performance, this research contributes to the literature in three main areas: 1) It offers theoretical contributions by linking EMA adoption to both financial and non-financial performance, thereby extending existing research on the role of EMA in corporate sustainability; 2) providing empirical evidence specific to the Nigerian oil sector, on the impact of EMA adoption in an emerging economy context, which has been underexplored in previous studies; 3) the research design, which focus on a longitudinal analysis of listed oil companies, provides valuable insights into how EMA adoption evolves over time and its sustained effects on operating performance; and 4) it proposes practical recommendations for policymakers and industry stakeholders on how to improve EMA adoption to drive sustainability and economic performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Environmental Management Accounting (EMA)

Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) is a strategic tool that helps firms manage their environmental impacts by continuously measuring environmental costs and benefits (Vasiu, 2023). It integrates both internal cost control and external financial reporting to manage environmental risks alongside traditional financial metrics (Jamil et al., 2015). EMA has evolved beyond its initial focus on pollution control to include broader aspects like resource efficiency and sustainability initiatives (Christ & Burritt, 2023). It aids companies in making strategic decisions about environmental investments and compliance with regulatory standards (Lüdeke-Freund, 2020).

2.2. Operating Performance

Operating performance refers to how efficiently an organization uses its resources to achieve strategic objectives (Achoki, 2024). It encompasses both financial and non-financial performance, both of which are essential for maintaining competitiveness and sustainability (Taouab & Issor, 2019).

2.2.1. Financial Performance

Financial performance involves the management of financial resources, including profitability, cost control, and return on investment (Mihai, 2023). Key performance indicators (KPIs) include net profit margin, operating income, and earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT) (Neely, 2018). In the oil industry, financial performance is influenced by production efficiency, market conditions, and

regulatory compliance. Effective operational practices can reduce downtime and improve cost efficiency, leading to enhanced financial stability (Abdelwhab Ali et al., 2019).

2.2.2. *Non-Financial Performance*

Non-financial performance focuses on metrics like productivity, quality, safety, and environmental impact. It offers a broader view of an organization's sustainability efforts (Muchran & Idrawahyuni, 2024). Productivity measures resource efficiency, while quality metrics assess the standard of goods and services. Safety performance is critical in high-risk industries like oil and gas, and environmental impact metrics, such as emissions and waste management, are crucial for assessing sustainability (Gonçalves & Silva, 2021).

2.3. Adoption of EMA in Nigerian Companies

The adoption of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) in the Nigerian oil sector has garnered significant attention due to the sector's substantial environmental impact and the increasing regulatory and societal demand for sustainable practices. Several empirical studies have explored the adoption of EMA in Nigeria's oil sector, highlighting varying levels of implementation across companies. For instance, a study by Edeh et al. (2020) found that while some oil companies have begun integrating EMA into their financial and management accounting systems, the adoption rate remains relatively low. The study pointed out that multinational oil companies operating in Nigeria, such as Shell and Chevron, tend to adopt more comprehensive EMA practices compared to local firms due to international pressures and corporate governance standards. Adeleye et al. (2019) conducted an empirical investigation of the adoption of EMA in the Nigerian oil industry and found that 45% of the oil companies surveyed had implemented some form of environmental accounting practices. However, the scope of EMA adoption was limited primarily to compliance with environmental regulations, with fewer companies using EMA as a tool for strategic decision-making. The study suggested that multinational oil companies were more likely to adopt EMA practices compared to indigenous companies due to stricter compliance standards and global reporting frameworks like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI).

The adoption of EMA in Nigerian oil companies is influenced by several factors, including regulatory pressure, corporate governance, and stakeholder demands. Adeyemi (2022) found that companies facing intense regulatory scrutiny and public pressure were more likely to adopt EMA practices to manage their environmental liabilities. The study revealed that corporate governance structures, particularly the presence of sustainability committees, were significantly associated with the extent of EMA adoption in oil companies. Another key factor influencing EMA adoption is the availability of resources and technical expertise. An empirical study by Egbunike and Okoro (2020) highlighted that many Nigerian oil companies lacked the financial and technical capacity to fully integrate EMA into their operations. The study also found that companies with better access to environmental data and expertise were more likely to implement EMA practices. Additionally, the availability of management support was a critical determinant of successful EMA adoption, as organizations with strong leadership commitment to environmental sustainability exhibited more comprehensive EMA practices.

Despite its potential benefits, the adoption of EMA in Nigeria's oil sector faces several challenges. A prominent issue is the lack of regulatory enforcement and inadequate incentives for companies to adopt EMA practices (Adeyemi, 2022). Many oil companies view EMA as an additional cost rather than an opportunity for cost savings and efficiency improvements, limiting their willingness to invest in EMA systems. Another challenge is the limited availability of environmental data, which hinders accurate environmental costing and reporting (Ihenyen & Ayoola, 2021). Edeh et al. (2020) found that many Nigerian oil companies struggle to accurately quantify environmental costs and integrate them into their financial reports, which reduces the effectiveness of EMA practices. Additionally, the lack of standardized EMA frameworks and guidelines in Nigeria further complicates the adoption process, as companies are often unsure of which metrics and methodologies to apply.

2.4. EMA and Financial Performance

Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) is a strategic tool that integrates environmental costs into traditional accounting systems, helping organizations improve their environmental and financial

performance. Several empirical studies have explored the relationship between EMA adoption and the financial performance of companies. Theoretically, EMA is expected to contribute to improved financial performance by helping companies identify and manage environmental costs, reduce waste, improve resource efficiency, and enhance corporate reputation (Egbunike & Okoro, 2020). By integrating environmental costs into decision-making, EMA can lead to cost savings, better risk management, and increased profitability. This assumption has been tested in various Nigerian sectors, particularly in industries with high environmental impacts, such as oil and gas, manufacturing, and agriculture.

The oil and gas industry is one of the most environmentally sensitive sectors in Nigeria. Several studies have explored how EMA practices impact the financial performance of companies in this sector. For instance, a study by Edeh et al. (2020) investigated the adoption of EMA in oil companies and found a positive relationship between EMA practices and financial performance. The study reported that oil companies that implemented EMA experienced cost savings through more efficient resource utilization and waste reduction. Additionally, these companies showed improved profitability due to better risk management and compliance with environmental regulations, which reduced the likelihood of fines and penalties. In a similar study, Adeleye et al. (2019) examined the effect of EMA on the financial performance of oil companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The findings revealed that companies with higher levels of EMA adoption exhibited better financial outcomes, such as higher return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). The study suggested that these improvements were due to cost savings from environmental efficiency and the ability to attract environmentally conscious investors, which enhanced the companies' market value.

Conclusively, the empirical evidence indicates a positive relationship between the adoption of EMA and financial performance. Companies in environmentally sensitive sectors, such as oil, manufacturing, and agriculture, that have adopted EMA practices tend to experience cost savings, improved profitability, and enhanced corporate reputation. However, challenges such as lack of technical expertise and inadequate regulatory support limit the full potential of EMA in Nigeria. Despite these barriers, the adoption of EMA remains a valuable tool for companies seeking to improve their financial performance while enhancing their environmental sustainability.

2.5.EMA and Non-Financial Performance

Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) plays a significant role in shaping both the financial and non-financial performance of companies. Non-financial performance generally refers to aspects such as environmental performance, corporate reputation, stakeholder satisfaction, employee engagement, and operational efficiency, which are not directly tied to financial outcomes but can influence long-term sustainability and success. This review focuses on empirical studies examining the impact of EMA on non-financial performance in Nigerian companies. EMA is primarily designed to help organizations track and manage their environmental costs, which in turn improves their environmental performance. Studies have shown that companies that adopt EMA often experience significant improvements in reducing their environmental footprint. According to a study by Olaniyi and Adeyemi (2021), oil companies in Nigeria that implemented EMA practices reported lower emissions, reduced waste generation, and better resource utilization. The study highlighted that EMA enables companies to identify inefficiencies in resource use and take corrective actions, leading to improved environmental sustainability. In another study by Nwankwo and Okafor (2020), manufacturing firms in Lagos State were examined to assess the impact of EMA on environmental performance. The researchers found that firms that adopted EMA experienced notable improvements in waste management practices and energy efficiency. These firms reduced their carbon footprint and water usage through systematic tracking of environmental costs and adopting eco-friendly processes. This aligns with the primary objective of EMA, which is to integrate environmental considerations into business decision-making.

Stakeholder satisfaction is another non-financial performance measure influenced by EMA adoption. Companies that implement EMA are better positioned to address the concerns of various stakeholders, including customers, investors, regulators, and communities, regarding environmental sustainability. This helps build stronger relationships with stakeholders and enhances overall stakeholder satisfaction.

In a study by Oluwaseun and Balogun (2021), the authors investigated the relationship between EMA and stakeholder satisfaction in Nigerian agricultural companies. The study found that firms with EMA practices experienced higher levels of stakeholder engagement and satisfaction. Specifically, these companies were better able to meet the expectations of regulators and environmental advocates by reducing their environmental impact and improving transparency in reporting environmental costs. As a result, they faced fewer regulatory pressures and were more likely to attract partnerships with environmentally conscious stakeholders.

EMA not only affects external stakeholders but also plays a role in influencing internal stakeholders, such as employees. Companies that adopt EMA practices often see improved employee engagement, particularly in environmentally sensitive sectors like oil, agriculture, and manufacturing (Mihai, 2023). By involving employees in sustainability initiatives and environmental cost management, companies can foster a sense of responsibility and ownership among their workforce. A study by Ibekwe and Adigwe (2020) explored the impact of EMA on employee engagement in Nigerian oil companies. The study revealed that companies that adopted EMA practices had higher levels of employee engagement in environmental initiatives. Employees in these companies were more motivated to contribute to sustainability goals, leading to improved operational efficiency and a sense of pride in the company's environmental stewardship. The research suggested that EMA could serve as a tool for enhancing employee morale by integrating sustainability into the corporate culture.

Conclusively, empirical evidence indicates that EMA significantly enhances non-financial performance by improving environmental performance, stakeholder satisfaction, and employee engagement. EMA adoption allows companies to manage their environmental risks more effectively, leading to better relations with stakeholders and improved operational outcomes. Despite the challenges associated with EMA adoption, such as lack of expertise and regulatory frameworks, the benefits in terms of non-financial performance are substantial.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. Institutional Theory

Institutional Theory posits that organisations are influenced by external forces like regulations, societal norms and industry pressures. These shape organisations' structure, behaviour and practices. This theory emphasizes the role of isomorphism. Isomorphism refers to the process by which organizations in similar fields tend to adopt similar practices to conform to external expectations and avoid illegitimacy (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). In the context of the Nigerian oil sector, Institutional Theory is highly relevant because oil companies face regulatory, environmental and societal pressures to adopt sustainable practices like EMA. The Nigerian government has introduced several environmental laws and policies to curb pollution and environmental degradation caused by oil exploration. Regulatory body like the Nigerian Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) enforce these regulations, pushing companies to adopt EMA to avoid sanctions and maintain their legitimacy.

Additionally, societal expectations have increased regarding the environmental responsibility of companies, especially in resource-intensive industries like oil. The adoption of EMA can enhance a company's reputation, meet stakeholder expectations and align with international environmental standards. This theory explains how these external pressures drive companies to integrate EMA into their operational processes, ultimately improving their non-financial performance, such as environmental performance and stakeholder relations.

3.2. Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV)

The Natural Resource-Based View (NRBV) extends the traditional Resource-Based View (RBV) by emphasizing the strategic importance of environmental capabilities. It argues that companies that manage their natural resources effectively, by adopting practices like EMA, can build a competitive advantage (Hart, 1995). The NRBV posits that by integrating environmental considerations into the firm's core strategy, companies can reduce waste, increase operational efficiency and enhance their environmental and financial performance. In the Nigerian oil sector, which is heavily dependent on

natural resources, the NRBV is highly relevant as it links environmental performance to competitive advantage. Oil companies that adopt EMA to track and manage their environmental impacts are likely to improve their resource efficiency and reduce environmental risks, which can lead to cost savings, improved operations and better stakeholder relations. For instance, effective waste management and pollution reduction can enhance a company's operational efficiency. This in turn positively affects its financial performance. Additionally, the adoption of EMA aligns with global environmental concerns, helping oil companies in Nigeria meet international environmental standards and gain sustainable competitive advantages. This is particularly important in the oil sector, where environmental degradation can lead to significant reputational damage and financial losses due to penalties and cleanup costs.

For this study, Institutional Theory is particularly useful in explaining why Nigerian oil companies adopt EMA due to regulatory and societal pressures, while NRBV offers insights into how these practices can enhance their operational efficiency and competitive positioning.

4. Methodology

4.1. Research Design

This study employed longitudinal and ex-post facto research designs. Longitudinal research design involves collecting data over an extended period, allowing us to observe how the adoption of EMA practices has impacted financial and non-financial performance over time. This is particularly useful since this research is about studying changes in environmental practices and their outcomes. Additionally, it enables us to track trends and analyse whether oil companies' performance improves as they adopt and refine EMA practices. An ex-post facto design is useful because it allows us to investigate the impact of EMA retrospectively, without manipulating variables. Since we are analysing the effect of EMA practices on performance, this design fits well because the cause (EMA adoption) has already occurred, and we are examining its effects, and this allow us to gather historical data on EMA adoption and performance metrics and analyse the relationships between them.

The study only employed secondary data collected from the annual reports and financial statements of the listed oil companies in Nigeria. They include records on environmental costs, operation performance measures as well as other financial indicators. However, other information was gathered from industry reports publications, academic journals, and those provided by the relevant regulatory bodies. The use of secondary data is justified since it provides consistent and reliable information over a period, which are necessary in carrying out a cross-sectional study.

The population of this study comprises all oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). As at the time of the study, there are 8 listed oil and gas companies on the NGX. The study employs a purposive sampling technique to select six oil firms as samples for this study. The firms selected are the firms that have consistently reported their environmental accounting practices over the study period. The selection criteria ensure that the sampled firms have sufficient data on EMA practices and operating performance metrics, allowing for a robust analysis of the impact of EMA on operational outcomes. The selected firms are: Conoil Plc., MRS Oil Nigeria Plc., Eterna Plc., Japaul Oil and Gas Services Plc, Total Energies, and Seplat Energy.

4.2. Measurement of Variables

Environmental Management Accounting (Independent Variable): This study adopted the approach of Adeyemi (2022) to measure environmental management accounting (EMA), which was measured by donations and environment-related expenses by the oil companies.

Financial Performance (Dependent Variable): In accordance with the approach of Esther and Isaiah (2023), this variable proxied with returns on assets (ROA), which was measured as net income divided by total assets, and earnings per share (EPS), which was measured as net income minus dividends on preferred shares divided by average outstanding shares.

Non-Financial Performance (Dependent Variable): In accordance with the approach of Taouab and Issor (2019), this variable was proxied with market size, which was measured as the total number of customers.

Control Variables: In line with the approach of Adeyemi (2022), the study included two control variables; firm size, measured as the logarithm of total assets, and leverage, measured as debt-to-total asset ratio.

4.3. Model Specification

4.3.1. EMA and Financial Performance

This is to test the effect of EMA practices on financial performance of oil companies under study in terms of Return on Assets (ROA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS). The models are specified as follows:

$$\text{Model 1: ROA}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EMA}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{SIZ}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Model 2: EPS}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EMA}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{SIZ}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

ROA_{it} = Return on total assets of the firm

EPS_{it} = Earnings Per Share available to the firm

EMA_{it} = The extent of the application of Environmental Management Accounting practices of firms

SIZ_{it} = The size of the Firm

LEV_{it} = Leverage of the firm

β₀ = Intercept

β₁, β₂, β₃ = Coefficients of the independent and control variables

ε_{it} = Error

4.3.2. EMA and Non-Financial Performance

The second model is an attempt to ascertain what changes EMA practices bring to non-financial performance, particularly in terms of Market Size (MKS) that defines the company's standing in the market share. The model is specified as follows:

$$\text{Model 3: MKS}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EMA}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{SIZ}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{LEV}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Where:

MKS_{it} = Market share of a firm

EMA_{it} = EMA practices in the firm

SIZ_{it}: This is the size of the firm of Firm

LEV_{it} = Leverage of the firm

β₀ = Intercept

β₁, β₂, β₃ = Coefficients of the independent and control variables

ε_{it} = Error term

4.4. Data Analysis Technique

In order to evaluate the level of adoption of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) practices among the selected oil companies in Nigeria, a descriptive analysis was conducted using frequency distributions, percentages, and averages to summarize and describe the level of EMA adoption.

In examining the effect of EMA on financial performance as well as the effect EMA on non-financial performance, panel data regression analysis was used to measure the significance and direction of the

relationship among these variables. Data was collected from annual reports of listed companies spanning 2014 to 2023. Relevant variables included financial metrics (Return on Assets, Earnings Per Share) and non-financial metrics (e.g., Market Size) as dependent variables, with EMA, leverage (LEV), and firm size (SIZE) as the main independent variables. Before analysis, the dataset was assessed for missing values, outliers, and multicollinearity.

We employed both fixed and random effects models to determine the relationship between EMA, LEV, SIZE, and performance indicators. The Hausman test was conducted to decide between the fixed-effects and random-effects models, ensuring the most appropriate model choice. Each model was evaluated based on statistical significance (p-values) of the coefficients, and model fit was assessed through R-squared values and Adjusted R-squared values. The coefficients were interpreted based on their direction, magnitude, and statistical significance, linking findings to the study hypotheses and theoretical frameworks.

5. Results and Interpretation

5.1. The Extent of Adoption of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) Practices Among Oil Companies in Nigeria

Figure 1 below shows the level of implementation of EMA practices by six Nigerian oil firms: Conoil Plc., MRS Oil Nigeria Plc., Eterna Plc., Total Energies, Seplat Energy, and Japaul Oil and Gas Services Plc between year 2014 to 2023. The figures show the proportion of total revenues that is allocated to EMA practices. Conoil is the only company that account for its health, safety and environmental expenses over the years, donation was used as a substitute variable for the other companies for the purpose of determining the extent of EMA adoption.

From the data presented, Japaul has the highest level of EMA adoption with an average allocation of 0.71% of its revenue over the years to rank 1st among the companies. The company's EMA expenditures reached their highest levels in 2017 at 2.87% which shows a strong commitment to environmental management during that period. Seplat is next with an average of 0.05% which makes it rank 2nd among the sample. The EMA expenditures of Seplat have been gradually rising and especially between the years 2016 and 2023 which also points to the company paying more attention to its environmental mandate.

MRS ranks third at an average EMA expenditure of 0.03%. The company's highest allocation occurred in 2020 when it dedicated 0.12% of its revenue to EMA, a considerable increase from previous years, suggesting a reactive approach to environmental management. Conoil, Eterna and Total have same rating occupying the 4th position touching an average expenditure of 0.02%. Conoil, which practices cost accounting for its environmental costs, has a steady but relatively low level of EMA commitment over the years, the same as Eterna and Total, which use donations as a form of EMA.

Overall, the extent of EMA adoption varies significantly among these companies, with Japaul and Seplat leading the way in environmental management efforts. The data suggests that while some companies have made substantial investments in EMA, others have taken a more conservative approach, either maintaining a consistent yet low level of expenditure or responding reactively to specific environmental demands or external pressures. This variation in EMA adoption reflects differing levels of commitment to environmental management across the Nigerian oil sector.

In general, the level of EMA adoption differs among these firms. From the collected data, it became evident that although some companies invested a significant amount of resources in EMA, others remain meagre or engage in reactive spending, indicating their hesitance in environmental stimuli and changes. This shows that organizations in the Nigerian oil sector have not been committed to the implementation of environmental management as seen from the variation in EMA adoption. The data suggests companies such as Japaul and Seplat are more assertive in implementing environmentally friendly strategies which may be due to legal mandates, pressure from their clients, or because their organisational culture emphasises conservation. While on the other hand, Eterna, Total, and Conoil exhibit less proactively, which could be because of the different goals, resource deployment policies, or the way they have perceived the significance of environmental management.

This analysis shows that, although awareness exists on the role of environmental management accounting for the Nigerian oil industry, there is still limited application and implementation in corporate strategies. Firms with higher budgets might accrue long term advantages like improved company image, sound compliance with the law, and possibly better financial returns due to better utilization of resources and better disposal of waste products. On the other hand, those with relatively low EMA expenditure may have to modify their approach and strategies to better conform to best practice standards in the area of environmental management.

Figure 1. Percentage of revenue spent on EMA practices by oil companies from 2014 to 2023

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

5.2.Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the study variables shown in Table 1 give details of the general distribution of the data for the parameters used in this study. Sampling variables used include Return on Assets (ROA), Earnings Per Share (EPS), Market Size (MSZ), Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), Leverage(LEV), and Firm Size (SIZE). The analysis on each of the variables has been summarized by their mean, Median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, range, minimum and maximum values to determine the central tendency as well as variability in the data.

The Return on Assets (ROA), which depicts the level of profitability of the firms against the total overall asset value, has a mean of 0.00318 and a standard deviation of 0.26137. This shows that there was a relatively large difference in the levels of profitability of the sampled oil companies. The ROA distribution is right-skewed (Skewness = 2.11101), implying the fact that, while most of the firms have low profitability, there are some firms which report higher ROA, values ranging from -0.99553 to 1.50821.

Earnings Per Share (EPS) shows a mean of 80.62183 and a notably high standard deviation of 242.52162, indicating substantial variability in earnings performance across the firms. The result shows that the variable is positively skewed with a skewness of 3. 25060 indicating that the distribution is asymmetrical with some firms getting extreme values from -347 to 1387 in their EPS distribution. This indicates that most firms have low to moderate EPS, but there are some extraordinary firms, which post very high or very low values.

Market Size (MSZ) which was measured by the natural log of the number of customers, is a key variable to measure the non-financial performance of the firms. The variable has a sample mean of 9.37705 and a standard deviation of 2.57774. The results also reveal that the data has a very little negative skewness (Skewness = -0.57533), an indication of most of the firms have their market sizes close to the mean but

there are some a few firms with relatively larger market. The range of market size values spans from 5.27300 to 12.44391, indicating a broad variation in the market reach of these companies.

Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) expenditures show a mean of 10.08196, with a standard deviation of 1.46000. The data for EMA is left-skewed (Skewness= -0.82108) meaning that the majority of the firms are close to the mean value and there are very few firms with higher or lower values of EMA expenses. The values of EMA range from 5.49717 to 12.87902 suggesting the variability in the firms' practices in environmental management.

Leverage (LEV), computed as the ratio of total debt to total asset, has a mean of 0.72980 and a standard deviation of 0.32224. The positive value of the skewness (Skewness = 2.68715) shows that though majority of the firms use higher level of leverage, there are some firms that have considerably lower debt to total assets ratio. The leverage values range from 0.26928 to 2.593, which depicts a broad range of practices in financial management among the firms within the oil industry.

Finally, Firm Size (SIZE), expressed as the logarithm of total assets, has a mean of 7.93642 and a standard deviation of 0.56273. The positive coefficient of skewness (0.91152) can be interpreted to mean that while the majority of firms and their sizes are close to the mean, there are some firms that are significantly larger than the mean. The firm size ranges from 6.94311 to 9.48479, which is a clear indication of the fact that the firms included in the study are of different sizes.

These descriptive statistics give a good insight into the variables involved and act as a good background for subsequent analytical techniques such as correlation and regression to determine the association between EMA practices and the production performance of Nigeria's oil firms. The fact that many of the variables produced coefficients which were so significantly different in terms of variability and distribution indicate that the firms are very heterogeneous when it comes to profitability, the size of the market they are operating in, their financial structure and their intensity of environmental management.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics	ROA	EPS	MSZ	EMA	LEV	SIZE
Mean	0.00318	80.62183	9.37705	10.08196	0.72980	7.93642
Standard Error	0.03374	31.30941	0.33279	0.18849	0.04160	0.07265
Median	0.02753	5.61	10.60512	10.18067	0.69025	7.78916
Standard Deviation	0.26137	242.52162	2.57774	1.46000	0.32224	0.56273
Sample Variance	0.06831	58816.73743	6.64476	2.13161	0.10384	0.31667
Kurtosis	21.98556	14.51610	-1.37651	1.12217	9.36650	0.35304
Skewness	2.11101	3.25060	-0.57533	-0.82108	2.68715	0.91152
Range	2.50374	1734	7.17091	7.38185	1.95305	2.54168
Minimum	-0.99553	-347	5.27300	5.49717	0.26928	6.94311
Maximum	1.50821	1387	12.44391	12.87902	2.22232	9.48479
Sum	0.19076	4837.31	562.62307	604.91763	43.78821	476.18507
Count	60	60	60	60	60	60

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

5.3. Preliminary Tests

5.3.1. Correlation Matrix

The correlation analysis in table 2 highlights the relationships among the key variables in this study: Return on Asset (ROA), Earnings Per Share (EPS), Market Size (MSZ), Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), Leverage (LEV), Firm Size (SIZE). Notably, ROA has a moderate positive relationship with EPS (0.4674), this means that when firms improve their profitability, it similarly improves its EPS value. Nevertheless, a moderate negative relationship is revealed when ROA is correlated with LEV (-0.41009), which means that higher levels of leverage could potentially have a negative effect on profitability because of the costs linked to debt. Interestingly, ROA and EMA have

a weak positive correlation of 0.09184, suggesting that there is little association between the use of environmental management practices and the profitability of a firm.

Examining the other relationships, EPS is moderately positively related to both MSZ and SIZE at 0.21486 and 0.06751 respectively. This suggests that although large market and firm sizes may have a slightly positive effect on earnings per share, the res is minimal. This finding indicates the fact that the relationship between EPS and EMA is insignificant (0.00416), thereby implying that environmental management practices do not affect earnings per share. Also, there is a weak negative relationship between EPS and LEV (-0.2243) which means that the increase of leverage could slightly decline per share earnings.

There is a strong positive relationship between SIZE and EMA, ($r = 0.62773$) which indicates that firms with a large size are more inclined to engage in the use of environmental management accounting practices. This may be because larger firms may have more resources and incentives to undertake sustainability activities. On the other hand, EMA has a moderate but negative relationship with LEV (-0.31506), suggesting that firms investing in environmental practices may be less dependent on debt financing. The correlation coefficient between MSZ and EMA is positive 0.16948, which confirms that firms with large market size may pay a little more attention to the management of the environment.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix

	ROA	EPS	MSZ	EMA	LEV	SIZE
ROA	1					
EPS	0.4674	1				
MSZ	0.161983	0.214863	1			
EMA	0.091842	0.004156	0.169479	1		
LEV	-0.41009	-0.2243	-0.16418	-0.31506	1	
SIZE	0.162284	0.067512	-0.09825	0.627726	-0.4384	1

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

5.3.2. Unit Root Test

To ensure the reliability of the data and avoid spurious regression results, unit root tests were conducted on the variables of interest: Return on Asset (ROA), Earnings per Share (EPS), Market Size (MSZ), Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), Leverage (LEV) and Firm Size (SIZE). To test for stationarity, the Levin, Lin & Chu test as well as, Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat techniques were used. The result is presented in table 3.

The outcome also shows the evidence that all the variables are stationary at first differenced degree implying that they have no unit root at this level. For ROA, the Levin, Lin & Chu t^* test yielded a coefficient of -5.04250 with a probability value of 0.0000, confirming no unit root. Similarly, the EPS, MSZ, EMA, LEV, and SIZE variables demonstrated stationarity with significant coefficients and probability values across the tests. These findings confirm the suitability of these variables for further econometric analysis.

5.3.3. Hausman Test

Before the estimation of a panel regression, the Hausman test (see table 4) is used to make a choice between the fixed effect and the random effect model for the panel data analysis. Hausman test is used to detect which of these two models performs better. The null hypothesis of the Hausman test is that the random effect model performs better, while the alternative hypothesis states that the fixed effect model is preferred.

Model 1

For the first model, the result indicated that the Chi-Square statistic is 1.885, with 3 degrees of freedom as well as a p-value of 0.5966. Considering that the p-value is greater than the conventional significance level of 0.05, the results suggest that the random-effects model should be typically selected. However, the results showed a zero-variance issue, which means that the random effects have no variation. This reduces the random-effects model's reliability. Consequently, the fixed-effects model is selected as the most appropriate model, notwithstanding that p-value from the Hausman test not significant. This approach is consistent with best practices in circumstances when the random effects have minimal or zero volatility, since it implies that the fixed effects model will produce more reliable and consistent outcomes for the analysis.

Table 3. Unit Root Test Result

Variables	Methods of Test	Coefficient	Prob	Level	Discovery	Decision
ROA	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-5.04250	0.0000	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-	-	-	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
EPS	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-6.70500	0.0000	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.08750	0.0010	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
MSZ	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-19.0282	0.0000	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-9.83394	0.0000	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
EMA	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-7.02788	0.0000	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.80780	0.0001	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
LEV	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-6.70500	0.0000	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.08750	0.0010	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
SIZE	Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-3.72209	0.0001	1(0)	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-	-	-	No Unit Root	Stationary at 1st Difference

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

Table 4. Hausman Test Result for Model 1

Test Summary	Chi-Sq Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.	
Cross-section random	1.885005	3	0.5966	
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
EMA	-0.014338	-0.01427	0	0.3472
LEV	0.023353	0.023226	0	0.8111
SIZE	0.212293	0.211767	0.000003	0.7507

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

Model 2

For the second model, the test summary indicates a Chi-Square statistic of 0.542017 with a 3-degree of freedom as well as p-value of 0.9096 (see Table 5). A p-value greater than the conventional significance threshold (for example, 0.05) indicates no evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which supports the random-effects model. Considering that the overall p-value (0.9096) and variable-specific p-values all surpass 0.05, this Hausman test supports the random-effects model as the better fit for these data. This implies that random effects are more appropriate for explaining changes in the dependent variable across entities, assuming the unobserved individual effects have no correlation with the explanatory variables.

Table 5. Hausman Test Result for Model 2

Test Summary	Chi-Sq Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.	
Cross-section random	0.542017	3	0.9096	
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
EMA	-11.021999	-11.76028	13.226	0.8391
LEV	-206.426	-193.0783	576.75	0.5783
SIZE	162.400332	109.96817	5134	0.4643

Source: Authors’ Computation (2024)

Model 3

The test summary in Table 6 reveals a Chi-Square statistic of 3.85114 with 3 degrees of freedom as well as a p-value of 0.278. Given that the p-value (0.278) is larger than 0.05, we cannot reject the null hypothesis, indicating an apparent choice of the random-effects model over the fixed-effects model. The p-values for each variable are likewise larger than 0.05, and because all variable-specific p-values are above 0.05, none of the variables change significantly betwixt the fixed and random effects. Essentially, because the aggregate p-value is greater than 0.05, the Hausman test implies that the random-effects model is the better choice. This implies that individual variations between entities are best represented by random effects, and the assumption that unobserved individual effects have no correlation with the model's predictor variables is possibly valid.

Table 6. Hausman Test Result for Model 3

Test Summary	Chi-Sq Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.	
Cross-section random	3.85114	3	0.278	
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var(Diff.)	Prob.
EMA	-0.023675	-0.00793	0.000342	0.3948
LEV	-0.468464	-0.3421	0.006946	0.1295
SIZE	0.242172	0.002408	0.027652	0.1493

Source: Author’s computation

5.4.Effect of EMA on the Financial Performance of Oil Companies

The regression analysis conducted to evaluate the effect of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), leverage (LEV), and firm size (SIZE) on the financial performance of oil companies in Nigeria, as measured by Return on Assets (ROA), provides valuable insights.

5.4.1. Regression analysis for model 1

For Model 1, we analyse the fixed-effects regression results, which examine the impact of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), leverage (LEV), and firm size (SIZE) on the dependent variable. The estimated regression model in Table 7 shows that the intercept for the

relationship between Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) and Return on Assets (ROA) is -0.9517, indicating the constant value of ROA when all predictors are zero. The coefficient for EMA is -0.7033, indicating a strong positive relationship between EMA and ROA, and a p-value of 0.4851, indicating a non-statistical impact of EMA on the dependent variable (ROA). Leverage (LEV) has a significant negative effect on ROA with a coefficient of -3.3874 ($p = 0.0014$), indicating higher leverage leads to lower ROA. Firm size (SIZE) has a positive but insignificant impact on ROA, with a coefficient of 1.3214 ($p = 0.1923$). The R-squared value of 0.2397 indicates that 24% of the variation in ROA is explained by the model, though the Adjusted R-squared of 0.1205, after accounting for the number of predictors, reveals that only 12% of the variance is explained by the model. The standard error of 0.2451 suggests that moderate variability in ROA remains unaccounted for by the model. The F-statistic is 2.00997 with a p-value of 0.0638, slightly above the customary 0.05 threshold, suggesting that the model is on the verge of statistical significance overall. The Durbin-Watson value of 1.8175, which is near to two, shows that the residuals have negligible autocorrelation. In conclusion, in this fixed-effects model, leverage is statistically significant and negatively correlated with the dependent variable, implying that increased leverage may diminish the return on assets (ROA). However, neither EMA nor company size (SIZE) are statistically significant predictors of the dependent variable in this model. The model explains a modest portion of the variation in dependent variable, and adding relevant factors may allow for more explanatory power.

Table 7. Fixed Effect OLS Regression Analysis Result for Model 1

Variables	Pooled OLS t (pv)	Fixed effect t (pv)	Random Effect t (pv)
C	0.5767 (0.5664)	-0.9517 (0.3457)	0.5751 (0.5675)
EMA	-0.2827 (0.7784)	-0.7033 (0.4851)	-0.2820 (0.7790)
LEV	-3.1083 (0.0030)	-3.3874 (0.0014)	-3.0997 (0.0030)
SIZE	0.0313 (0.9751)	1.3214 (0.1923)	0.0312 (0.9752)
EFFECT SPECIFICATIONS			
CROSS SECTION FIXED (DUMMY VARIABLES)			
R-squared	0.239711		
Adjusted R-squared	0.12045		
S.E. of regression	0.24512		
Sum squared resid	3.064268		
Log-likelihood	4.099766		
F-statistic	2.00997		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.063825		
Mean dependent var	0.003179		
S.D. dependent var	0.261365		
Akaike info criterion	0.163341		
Schwarz criterion	0.477493		
Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.286223		
Durbin-Watson stat	1.817527		

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

5.4.2. Regression analysis for model 2

The regression model in Table 8 shows that the intercept for the relationship between Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS) is -0.5909, representing the expected EPS when all variables are zero. EMA has a small, negative, but statistically insignificant impact on EPS, with a coefficient of -0.4695 ($p = 0.6405$). This shows that EMA variations have no significant effect on the dependent variable in this model. Leverage (LEV) negatively impacts EPS, with a coefficient of -1.9084, and is marginally significant ($p = 0.0615$). Higher leverage may have a minor negative impact on the dependent variable, although this effect is not statistically significant at

conventional levels ($p < 0.05$). Firm size (SIZE) shows a positive but statistically insignificant effect on EPS, with a coefficient of 0.9343 ($p = 0.3542$). This result suggests that firm size has no meaningful impact on the dependent variable in this model. The R-squared value of 0.0767 suggests that only 7.67% of the variation in EPS is explained by the model. This little value indicates that additional variables that are not present in the model may be responsible for the bulk of the variance. The Adjusted R-squared of 0.0272 further emphasises the limited predicting power of the model. A standard error of 180.2110 highlights significant variability in EPS not captured by the model. In conclusion, the independent variables (EMA, LEV, SIZE) have minimal and statistically insignificant effects on EPS, with leverage showing a marginally significant negative relationship. The model's ability to predict EPS is weak, as reflected by the low R-squared values.

Table 8. Random Effect OLS Regression Analysis Result for Model 2

Variables	Pooled OLS t (pv)	Fixed effect t (pv)	Random Effect t (pv)
C	0.5834 (0.5620)	-0.8952 (0.3749)	-0.5909 (0.5570)
EMA	-0.4738 (0.6375)	-0.4355 (0.6651)	-0.4695 (0.6405)
LEV	-1.6921 (0.0962)	-1.9852 (0.0525)	-1.9084 (0.0615)
SIZE	0.0558 (0.9557)	1.1785 (0.2441)	0.9343 (0.3542)
Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.076667		
Adjusted R-squared	0.027203		
S.E. of regression	180.2110		
F-statistic	1.549956		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.211737		
Mean dependent var	17.22542		
S.D. dependent var	182.7134		
Sum squared resid	1818657		
Durbin-Watson stat	0.936632		

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

5.5. Effect of EMA on the Non-Financial Performance of Oil Companies

This section presents the regression results for the impact of EMA expenses on the non-financial performance of oil companies, as measured by market size. The analysis examines whether EMA practices contribute to the expansion or retention of the customer base in the oil industry.

5.5.1. Regression Model for Model 3

The regression analysis in Table 9 shows that the intercept for the relationship between Environmental Management Accounting (EMA), leverage (LEV), and firm size (SIZE) on market size (MSZ) is 5.5936, indicating the expected market size when all variables are zero. EMA has a significant negative impact on market size, with a coefficient of -1.1874 ($p = 0.02401$). LEV shows a positive but insignificant effect (coefficient = 0.4705, $p = 0.6398$), while firm size has a significant positive impact on market size (coefficient = 3.2377, $p = 0.0020$). The R-squared value of 17.22% suggests that the model explains a modest portion of the variation in market size, with an Adjusted R-squared of 12.78%. The standard error of 0.086631 indicates low variability in the market size not accounted for by the model. In summary, EMA has a significant negative effect on market size, while firm size significantly positively impacts market size, and leverage shows an insignificant positive relationship. The model explains a modest portion of the variation in market size among oil companies.

Table 9. Random Effect OLS Regression Analysis Result for Model 3

Variables	Pooled OLS t (pv)	Fixed effect t (pv)	Random Effect t (pv)
C	3.6672 (0.0005)	15.5774 (0.0000)	5.5936 (0.0000)
EMA	2.2988 (0.0253)	-1.1930 (0.2384)	-1.1874 (0.02401)
LEV	1.7307 (0.0890)	0.4730 (0.6382)	0.4705 (0.6398)
SIZE	2.5736 (0.0127)	3.2447 (0.0021)	3.2377 (0.0020)
Weighted Statistics			
R-squared	0.172183		
Adjusted R-squared	0.127836		
S.E. of regression	0.086631		
F-statistic	3.882609		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.013624		
Mean dependent var	0.08114		
S.D. dependent var	0.092762		
Sum squared resid	0.420272		
Durbin-Watson stat	1.333607		

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

6. Discussion

The results indicate a negative, though statistically insignificant, relationship between EMA and ROA as well as EPS. This finding aligns with studies such as Burritt and Schaltegger (2010), who argue that the short-term financial gains from EMA may be limited due to the high initial costs of adopting sustainable accounting practices. These costs, which include restructuring operations and investing in cleaner technologies, may temporarily lower profitability. Similarly, Deegan and Blomquist (2006) noted that while EMA is intended to improve long-term sustainability and reduce environmental costs, its immediate financial impact may not be positive, especially in sectors like oil where traditional operations are deeply embedded.

Contrary to the insignificant effect found in this study, some research shows a positive relationship between EMA and financial performance in the long run. Schaltegger et al. (2013) found that firms adopting EMA practices eventually experienced cost savings and enhanced profitability through efficiency improvements. However, the divergence in this study could be attributed to the unique challenges of the Nigerian oil industry, where environmental management practices may not yet be fully integrated into the financial decision-making process (Okoye & Egbunike, 2013).

Similarly, the regression analysis demonstrates a significant negative relationship between EMA and market size, suggesting that firms adopting EMA practices might face challenges in expanding their market presence. This contrasts with the findings of Qian et al. (2018), who argue that companies that integrate environmental management into their strategy tend to gain a competitive advantage, leading to market growth. However, in the context of the Nigerian oil sector, where environmental awareness may not yet be a major market driver, the results are understandable. Ojo (2020) points out that environmental sustainability is still a growing concern in Nigeria, and the market size of oil companies is more influenced by factors like oil prices and government regulations than by environmental initiatives.

The study also found that leverage has a consistently negative effect on both ROA and EPS, with a marginally significant negative impact on EPS. This is consistent with previous studies, such as Myers (1977), who argue that higher leverage reduces a firm's financial flexibility and increases its risk exposure, thus negatively affecting financial performance. In capital-intensive industries like oil, where external financing is common, firms with higher debt levels often face higher interest obligations, which can erode profits (Titman & Wessels, 1988).

Lastly, the results show that firm size has a positive and significant effect on market size but an insignificant impact on ROA and EPS. Larger firms may benefit from economies of scale and market dominance, which can enhance their market size. This finding is supported by prior research from Hart and Ahuja (1996), who argue that larger firms are more likely to adopt sustainability practices due to their resource availability, leading to better market positioning. However, the insignificant impact on financial metrics like ROA and EPS suggests that size alone does not guarantee financial performance, possibly due to inefficiencies and operational complexities in larger organizations (Pandey, 2010).

Overall, this study's findings are in line with some of the literature on EMA and its impact on financial and non-financial performance. While EMA practices are essential for long-term sustainability, their immediate financial benefits may be limited, especially in the context of the Nigerian oil industry. Moreover, leverage negatively affects financial performance, while firm size positively influences market positioning but does not guarantee improved financial outcomes. As the Nigerian oil sector continues to evolve, future studies could explore the longer-term effects of EMA adoption and the changing role of market forces in driving sustainability efforts.

7. Conclusion

The study surveyed the effects of Environmental Management Accounting (EMA) on the operating performance of listed oil companies in Nigeria for the period 2014- 2023. The study established that though EMA practices are gradually being implemented in these companies, the relationship between EMA practices and ROI and EPS is not significant. This implies that if there are any financial benefits of EMA, they may take a longer period to accrue or are even nullified by other forms of financial features like leverage which was found to have negative impacts to financial performance. Also, the slightly negative and significant correlation between EMA and non-financial performance, particularly market size, also provides an understanding of the significance of adopting sustainable practices beyond cost savings and financial gains. Corporate environmental management leads to improved corporate image and customer satisfaction that benefits the organizations and leads to a competitive edge in the market.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- The Nigerian oil firms should make more efforts to effectively implement the Environmental Management Accounting (EMA). This can be done by establishing effective EMA frameworks that are not only a reaction to the current legislation but, instead, are based on principles of sustainable development and efficient usage of resources.
- Companies should make also it a point to put into practice some training programs for the accountants and the management teams. This will guarantee that staff is well prepared to put in place and efficiently manage efficient managerial analysis (EMA) practices hence improving on environmentalism and financial performance.
- Specifically, using EMA data is not currently as effective as it could be for strategic decision-making. Companies should compensate for environmental costs and benefits in their accounting models as this will enhance decision-making for economic and environmental rationale.

Limitations of the Study

The study relied on publicly available data from listed oil companies in Nigeria. However, not all companies may fully disclose detailed information on their environmental management accounting (EMA) practices, leading to potential gaps in data. Moreover, the study focused solely on oil companies, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other industries. The unique characteristics of the oil industry, such as heavy regulatory scrutiny and environmental impact, may not reflect EMA's effect in other sectors. Additionally, the study examines the relationship between EMA and performance indicators over a specific period, potentially overlooking the long-term benefits of EMA practices. The short-term financial impacts may not capture the gradual improvements that EMA can bring to company performance. Furthermore, the model included only EMA, leverage, and firm size as predictors of financial and non-financial performance. Other factors, such as corporate governance, regulatory environment, and technological advancements, which may influence these performance

metrics, were not considered in the analysis. Lastly, the study mainly assessed market size as a proxy for non-financial performance. However, other non-financial performance indicators such as customer satisfaction, employee retention, and social responsibility initiatives were not considered.

Future research should consider a longer time frame to evaluate the long-term impact of EMA on both financial and non-financial performance. This would provide insights into the cumulative effects of EMA adoption on company sustainability. To enhance the generalizability of the findings, future studies should examine the impact of EMA on companies in other sectors, such as manufacturing, services, or technology. Comparative studies across industries would provide a broader understanding of EMA's influence. Further research should also explore other non-financial performance metrics, such as corporate social responsibility (CSR), environmental footprint reduction, and stakeholder engagement, and include additional variables, such as corporate governance practices, regulatory compliance, or technological advancements, to better understand the dynamics between EMA and performance.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Abdelwhab Ali, A., Selvam, D. D., Paris, L., & Gunasekaran., A. (2019). Key factors influencing knowledge sharing practices and its relationship with organizational performance within the oil and gas industry. *Journal of Knowledge Management* , 23(9), 1806-1837.
2. Achoki, M. P. (2024). The Impact of Design for the Environment Practices on Operational Performance: A Case of Food Manufacturing Companies in Kenya. *Management of Sustainable Development*, 16(1), 24-36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54989/msd-2024-0003>
3. Adeleye, I., Ojo, J. A., & Ojo, O. T. (2019). Environmental Management Practices in the Nigerian Oil Sector: Challenges and Opportunities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 23(1), 1216-1225.
4. Adeyemi, O. (2022). Environmental management accounting and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Environmental Accounting Journal*, 16(3), 45-59.
5. Asagunla, T. M., & Agbede, M. O. (2018). Oil revenue and output growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 4(6), 65-74.
6. Burritt, R. L., & Schaltegger, S. (2010). Sustainability accounting and reporting: Fad or trend? *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 23(7), 829-846.
7. Burritt, R. L., Hahn, T., & Schaltegger, S. (2002). Towards a comprehensive framework for environmental management accounting—Links between business actors and environmental management. *Australian Accounting Review*, 12(2), 39-50.
8. Burritt, R. L., Herzig, C., Schaltegger, S., & Viere., T. (2019). Diffusion of environmental management accounting for cleaner production: Evidence from some case studies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 22(4), 479-491.
9. Christ, K. L., & Burritt, R. L. (2023). Environmental management accounting: The significance of contingent variables for adoption. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 41(4), 163-173.
10. Deegan, C. (2002). The legitimising effect of social and environmental disclosures: A theoretical foundation. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 15(3), 282-311.
11. Deegan, C., & Blomquist, C. (2006). Stakeholder influence on corporate reporting: An exploration of the interaction between WWF-Australia and the Australian minerals industry. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 31(4-5), 343-372.
12. DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The iron cage revisited: Institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147-160.
13. Ebeku, K. S. (2018). Environmental regulation in Nigeria's oil sector: A critique. *Environmental Law Review*, 15(4), 243-268.

14. Ebimobowei, A. (2022). Oil revenue and economic growth of Nigeria: 1990–2019. *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(1), 17-46.
15. Edeh, N. I., Chukwuma, P. M., & Ishaku, D. (2020). Environmental Accounting Practices of Oil Companies in Nigeria: Does Greening the Environment Matter? *Vocational and Technical Education Journal*, 2(2), 305-315.
16. Egbunike, F. C., & Okoro, D. O. (2020). Environmental management accounting practices and financial performance in the Nigerian oil industry. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 15(3), 215-230.
17. Esther, I. O., & Isaiah, O. O. (2023). Environmental Accounting Practice and Financial Performance of Listed Aviation Firms in Nigeria. *Asian journal of economics, business and accounting*, 23(13), 70-80.
18. Gerged, A. M., Zahoor, N., & Cowton, C. J. (2024). Understanding the relationship between environmental management accounting and firm performance: The role of environmental innovation and stakeholder integration – Evidence from a developing country. *Journal of Management Accounting Research*, 62(1), 1-14..
19. Gonçalves, A., & Silva, C. (2021). Looking for sustainability scoring in apparel: A review on environmental footprint, social impacts and transparency. *Energies*, 14(11), 3032
20. Hart, S. L. (1995). A natural-resource-based view of the firm. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(4), 986-1014.
21. Hart, S. L., & Ahuja, G. (1996). Does it pay to be green? An empirical examination of the relationship between pollution prevention and firm performance. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 5(1), 30-37.
22. Ibekwe, I. M., & Adigwe, C. J. (2020). Impact of environmental management accounting on employee engagement in Nigerian oil companies. *Journal of Environmental Accounting and Management*, 12(3), 72-89.
23. Ihenyen, C. J., & Ayoola, F. O. (2021). EMA practices and financial performance in the Nigerian financial services sector. *Journal of Environmental Accounting and Management*, 29(1), 31-45.
24. James, I. E., & Sylvester, O. (2023). Effect of environmental performance disclosure on the profitability of the oil and gas industry in Nigeria. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 5(7), 135-149..
25. Jamil, C. Z., Mohamed, R., Muhammad, F., & Ali, A. (2015). Environmental management accounting practices in small medium manufacturing firms. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 17(2), 619-626.
26. Lüdeke-Freund, F. (2020). Towards a conceptual framework for sustainable business models. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 24(3), 118674.
27. Medeckytė, K., & Daiva, T. (2023). Development of environmental management accounting system: a conceptual approach. *Buhalterinės apskaitos teorija ir praktika*, 2-5.
28. Mihai, C. (2023). The Impact of Sustainable Reporting on the Financial Performance of Energy and Gas Companies Listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange. An Empirical Approach. *Management of Sustainable Development*, 15(1), 26-31. <https://doi.org/10.54989/msd-2023-0004>
29. Muchran, M., & Idrawahyuni, R. (2024). Analysis of Financial and Non-Financial Performance of Public Sector Organizations. *Contemporary Journal on Business and Accounting*, 4(1), 1-14.
30. Myers, S. C. (1977). Determinants of corporate borrowing. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 5(2), 147-175.
31. Neely, A. (2018). Performance measurement system design: Developing and testing a process-based approach. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 205(3), 61-72.

32. Nwankwo, B. N., & Okafor, J. (2020). Impact of environmental management accounting on environmental performance in Lagos manufacturing firms. *Journal of Sustainable Business Practices*, 8(1), 54-70.
33. Nwokeji, J. (2019). Environmental accounting and oil sector inefficiencies: A Nigerian perspective. *Oil and Gas Journal*, 7(3), 134-147.
34. Ojo, E. (2020). Environmental sustainability and its impact on market performance of oil companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 30(4), 56-72.
35. Okoye, E. I., & Egbunike, F. C. (2013). Environmental cost accounting: A technique for enhancing corporate environmental reporting in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 12(1), 42-47.
36. Olaniyi, A. O., & Adeyemi, F. M. (2021). Environmental management accounting and environmental performance of Nigerian oil firms. *Journal of Environmental Sustainability*, 9(2), 119-134.
37. Oluwaseun, O., & Balogun, T. (2021). Environmental management accounting and stakeholder satisfaction in Nigerian agricultural companies. *Journal of Environmental Economics*, 10(2), 39-58.
38. Otu, U. A., Okon, A. M., & Nnanna, O. L. (2018). Oil Companies Performance and Environmental Accounting Reporting in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 8(1), 1-8.
39. Pandey, I. M. (2010). *Financial Management*. Vikas Publishing House.
40. Polycarp, S. U. (2019). Environmental Accounting and Financial Performance of Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(10), 192-202
41. Qian, W., Hörisch, J., & Schaltegger, S. (2018). Environmental management accounting and its effects on carbon management and disclosure quality. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 174(4), 1608-1619.
42. Slack, N. (2019). *Operations and Process Management: Principles and Practice for Strategic Impact*. (2nd ed.). Pearson Education.
43. Schaltegger, S., & Burritt, R. (2017). *Sustainability accounting and reporting: Theory and practice*. Springer.
44. Schaltegger, S., Burritt, R., & Petersen, H. (2017). *An introduction to corporate environmental management: Striving for sustainability*. Routledge.
45. Schaltegger, S., Lüdeke-Freund, F., & Hansen, E. G. (2013). Business cases for sustainability: The role of business model innovation for corporate sustainability. *International Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*, 7(2), 95-119.
46. Shell Nigeria. (2022). *Sustainability report*. Shell Nigeria.
47. Titman, S., & Wessels, R. (1988). The determinants of capital structure choice. *Journal of Finance*, 43(1), 1-19.
48. Vasiu, D.E. (2023). Environmental, Social and Governance Performance on the Romanian Capital Market. *Management of Sustainable Development*, 15(2), 80-86. <https://doi.org/10.54989/msd-2023-0019>.

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